

BIRTH PHOTOGRAPHY AS A NORMAL MATERNITY FACILITY AT PMB**Desi Latifatul Hasanah**

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Abstract: Birth photography is a new form of birth art, the emergence of birth photography as an expression of a woman's birth experience that is centered on women. Photos become a means of imaginative adventure for human experience, communication between humans and themselves, between people and even between generations. This birth memoir is a form of celebration and gift for future children, parents, or anyone else for the moment of childbirth which only happens once in a woman's life even if there are subsequent births. With current technological advances, birth documentation as a medium for capturing beautiful memories of childbirth can be easily done, using a camera or a smartphone. The data source in this study uses a literature review method which comes from several sources, both national and international journals, using published articles from Google Scholar, Radiation Oncology Journal, PubMed, and Elsevier. In this research, birth photography is used as a facility for mothers going through normal childbirth. The aim is to entice mothers to become more interested and brave in going through natural childbirth with professional midwives at PMB.

Keywords: birth photography, normal birth, photography, mother, baby

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Introduction

Photography is a good activity that is increasingly popular and is by everyone. Everyone can easily compete to capture every second of their experience with camera shots. As time goes by, the photography business is also growing rapidly. Nowadays, almost everyone can capture moments with a camera, whether an expert camera or a pocket camera or cellphone camera. The advancement of the features provided makes it very easy for the clients. Along with the development of interest, both among photography experts and photography lovers, various new types or varieties of photography have emerged. One classification of photography that is starting to emerge and become a pattern in the eyes of the public is birth photography. [1]

Birth photography is another type of birth craftsmanship, the rise of birth photography as a statement of a woman's introduction to a female-focused experience of the world. Looking for a verifiable excursion regarding the presence of birth photography, it has actually been around for quite some time in the book "The Family of Man – The greatest photographic exhibition of all time – 503

pictures from 68 countries" created by Edward Steichen for the Gallery of Current Workmanship, New York, this book contains various photos that depict life from birth to death with an emphasis on people's daily lives with themselves, their families, communities and where we live, including photos of a woman's birthing process. [2]

Photographic is a visual record of an object, incident, or event using the photographic method. Apart from providing accurate and valid data, photographic works also have high narrative value. Birth photography or birth photos are taken to capture a portrait of a mother who is struggling while giving birth to her child. Birth portraits are very important because birth is a big thing that is important to pay attention to and appreciate, because on that day it is not only a small child who is born into the world as a human being, but also the people around him who experience a change in status too. Childbirth is not just about the birth of a child into the world. [3]

Childbirth is the birth of a mother, a father, a relative, a grandparent, etc. Photography has always been associated with human experience, including the moment of birth. The memoir is written as a story or description of meetings that emphasize the life of a mother contained in existing photographs apart from everything else about the birth. These photos are then introduced as important travel notes that can be used as examples and enjoyed by others. Photos become a method of creative experience for human experience, correspondence between humans and themselves, between individuals, even between ages. This birth memoir is a form of celebration and gift for future children, family, or other people for the description of childbirth which may occur once in a woman's life regardless of subsequent births. [4]

Childbirth is a natural, normal and healthy process. Midwives believe that the appropriate model of midwifery care or care in childbirth assistance for pregnant women can help and maintain a normal birth process. It is true that a woman should receive the best service from expert health workers, so that the development of her condition can be monitored and prevented and handled well if a disorder occurs. Expanding the normal birth rate means reducing unnecessary SC cases. [5]

The idea of normal delivery is to reduce the referral system. With advances in science and innovation, more and more technological tools can be used to balance and maintain the concept of normal childbirth. Midwives should accompany the development of pregnant women well so that after the birth process occurs gradually the mother feels calm and at ease and avoids excessive worry. This obstetric consideration aims to reduce the incidence of perineal rupture, SC cases, and other unnecessary actions. This physiological delivery results in a shorter labor time, reduced incidence of fetal distress, reduced postpartum hemorrhage, lower incidence of perineal rupture (15%), and incidence of CS (<1%). [6]

It is hoped that a normal or natural birth process will not have any indication of risk to the mother or fetus during the birth process, therefore during the birth process the midwife will really focus on helping the birth process properly until the fetus is born. Maternity care services routinely have important control over the mother's condition because it influences the birthing process. An easy delivery will definitely prevent the mother from experiencing the trauma of giving birth and provide a beautiful memoir for a mother to always remember. [7]

With today's increasingly innovative technological advances, birth documentation as a mechanism for capturing beautiful memories of childbirth can be done easily, whether using a camera or cellphone. Birth photography is seen as a sacred moment that will not be repeated. Therefore, birth photography has become a habitual pattern among millennial parents. Birth documentation should be done yourself, or by involving the services of a professional photographer so that the results of the birth documentation are more artistic and imaginative so that the family can focus on providing psychological support to the mother during the birth process. [8]

On this basis, birth photography became the author's interest as a way to encourage pregnant women to be more interested in having a normal birth at PMB because birth is actually a natural process and will be enjoyable if it is well prepared and handled by professional health workers. Through birth photography, it is hoped that mothers can remember, immortalize and retell to their children about the birth process, full of joy and emotion at welcoming the birth of their baby. [9]

Methods

The type of research used is descriptive research with a literature review method to collect, identify, and interpret "Birth Photography as a Normal Maternity Facility at PMB". Data sources for research using the literature review method come from several sources, both national and international journals, using published articles from Google Scholar, Radiation Oncology Journal, PubMed, and Elsevier.

Search for published articles on this research on Google Scholar and Pubmed using the following keywords: birth photography, normal delivery, and Independent Midwife Practice. This literature review uses literature published in 2020-2023 which can be accessed in full text in pdf format. The journal criteria selected for review were journal articles containing a theme related to "Birth Photography as a Normal Maternity Facility at PMB".

The results of the literature review will be explained following the following themes:

1. Purpose of birth photography
2. Benefits of normal delivery and conditions for being able to give birth normally

Of the twenty journals obtained, fifteen research journals were obtained with five journals that best met the criteria. Then, the five journals were collected and a journal summary was created as in the following table:

Table 1. Journal Summary

Nu .	Writer's name	Publication Year	Journal Title	Contents
1.	Andi Arina Maulina, Lasakajaya Sari, Erlina Novianti	2020	Fotografi Cerita Naratif pada Give Birth Photography	This photography was created using a photographic approach with captions created and includes opening, content and closing photo segments. In early visual works, high contrast photography, accessible light, and later the EDFAT technique were applied in these compositions. It is believed that this work can

				provide a top to bottom message about the struggles of mothers in the birthing process.
2.	Kartikasari Yudaningsari	2020	Etika Fotografi dalam Proses Dokumentasi Kelahiran	There are many photography financial managers who handle birth documentation services, but incidentally, not all photography artists understand a set of basic principles that can be used as guidelines for birth registration. General rules relate to the documentation cycle in the birth climate, a set of principles governing with the client and the client's family, regarding body parts to be reported as well as a set of rules when transferring birth photos via online entertainment.
3.	Galuh Paramithasari	2021	Memoar Persalinan dalam Birth Photography	The presence of birth photography makes it possible to carry out various goals and jobs, both individual and with social and business value. The aim of this work is to review the events and encounters of a mother who is pregnant with a child as a form of documentation of the struggle, strength, deep journey and love of a mother in giving birth to her child. So this creation is complemented by narrative photography actions that apply visual nuances at an ideational and specialized level. The ideational level is the stylistic value associated with a thought, thought or idea, while the special level is the extraction of taste values through process strategies in making photography.
4.	Rivka Ribak, Anat Leshnick	2022	'A powerful, spiritual, win-win situation': commercial authenticity in professional birth photography	Recalling meetings with photographic artists and clients, an examination of the diaries presents three basic strands of birth photography as narrative and pioneering efforts: standard depictions of unusual events; openness to imply meeting; and the commercialization of the sacred. To the extent that they are satisfying, birth photos present a limited and traditional image making them suitable for family collections and the photographer's online entertainment portfolio.

5.	Retmi Eka Sasmita, Syukrianti Syahda, Fitri Handayani	2023	Asuhan Kebidanan Ibu Bersalin Normal Di PMB Ketra Delfi	The delivery system is something that is physiological, there is no gap between reality and hypothesis in carrying out routine maternity care for pregnant mothers which is carried out at PMB Ketra Delfi, Koto Tibun City, on July 5 2020 for Mrs. F with P3 A0 H3 mature. 37 years old, so it can be assumed that the maternity services provided to Mrs. F has been running well without any complications and obstacles in working. The work takes around 6 hours. The work starts from stage I to stage IV, the results of the studies and observations are combined into partographs and documentation of birth assistance care outlined in the birth process.
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Departing from these journals, the author wants to realize birth photography facilities for women giving birth normally at PMB by collaborating with professional women photographers or with midwives with good photography skills so that there is a feeling of comfort for pregnant women in the birth photography process. Apart from that, it is hoped that this birth photography facility will be able to open up new job opportunities for suitable professional workers.

Result and Discussion

The study of birth photography allows the author to explore the intersection between entrepreneurship and childbirth. Specifically, the author wants to learn about the images produced when midwives collaborate with female photographers to document the birth process of babies. In birth photography, the wishes and comfort of a birthing mother are prioritized because this can affect the smoothness of the normal birth process. The role of the midwife here is to provide assistance and preparation for pregnant women so that they are able to give birth normally. With birth photography, it is hoped that it can encourage pregnant women to be more interested in having a normal birth at PMB. [10]

Normal delivery has advantages that are very beneficial for the mother's comfort, for example faster recovery, lower possibility of complications, and building a closer relationship or bond between mother and child. However, there are several conditions that are important requirements for a normal delivery to occur, including:

1. The baby's development is normal during pregnancy and there are no complications experienced by the fetus and mother
2. Head presentation allows for normal delivery. Pregnant women can give birth normally if the baby is in a cephalic presentation which allows normal delivery.
3. The previous normal birth process occurred without complications, if the previous birth was via SC then you must meet the requirements for a VBAC. [11]

Based on the journals studied by the author, it shows that photographers can give birthing mothers a birth story that is personally meaningful, an aesthetic memory object (especially in the current digital era), and the intimacy experienced by both of them even though it is only temporary. Apart from that, photographers must also apply photography ethics [12]. Ethics is a very important thing, especially in relation to other parties. In the world of photography, ethics is

still an interesting topic of discussion. Taking photos in certain areas must pay attention to applicable rules and ethics. In the context of birth documentation, which is generally carried out at PMB, you must follow the rules that apply in each PMB. PMB is a place of public service, therefore don't let taking photos in the PMB environment disrupt the performance and service of PMB staff, especially if it violates the privacy of clients and their families [13].

The results of the creation of photographic works will be divided into 3 parts of the birth process, including pre-natal, labor and post-natal.

1. Pre-natal

In the pre-natal stage, the moments that are used as photographic objects usually include the atmosphere of the delivery room/room, the moment of pregnancy with the partner, the time to enter labor starting in the 1st stage of labor, the written identity of the client, and the tools prepared to assist the process. labor.

2. Childbirth

At the birth stage, the moments that are used as photographic objects usually include the birthing process, actions taken by the midwife, removal of the umbilical cord, IMD (Early Initiation of Breastfeeding) moments.

3. Post-natal

The post-partum stages, the moments that are used as photographic objects, usually include the period after giving birth when the placenta is born until 24 hours after the birth process. His photo works immortalize babies who have been born, including measurements of the baby's head circumference, baby's weight, right and left foot prints, and photos of happiness with the family or midwives after the baby is born. [14]

From the results of this photography, clients will receive photos of their birthing process which have been produced and cropped according to the concept of the sacredness of the birthing process. It can be interpreted literally that, birth photography is indeed a medium in visual form which is expected to provide messages about the birthing process, not only to children, mothers, fathers, even friends and the general public can also understand photographic works as a form of appreciation for the mother's struggle. That can be remembered one day or shown to their child when the child understands. [15]

Conclusion

Birth photography is very interesting and popular among people so it is easily accepted by the wider community. Birth photography is a genre of photography that can convey a message well and precisely, meaning that everyone will understand and understand the message in the photo. It is nothing but the struggle of a mother who struggled for nine months and risked her life during the birthing process. Through a photographic approach, this work invites readers to find out in general the process of normal childbirth. Through this work, it is hoped that it will be able to directly convey the message of the meaning of struggle, affection, happiness and hope from parents to their children. Each photo of the birth process itself can be described as a whole or one by one from each photo taken, both in terms of meaning, function, purpose, photography science, data, and also the final result of this birth photography work.

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